

Cleavage of Pentaphenyl Arsenic and Antimony Derivatives with Halogens and Interhalogens

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Facile and specific cleavage of metal-carbon bond(s) has been found to occur when pentaphenyl-arsenic or -antimony derivatives are treated with halogens (Br_2, I_2) and inter-halogens (ICl , IBr) under controlled conditions.

THOUGH the reaction involving the oxidative addition of electrophilic reagents have been extensively studied for stereospecific addition to triarylarisines and -stilbenes¹⁻³, reports regarding the cleavage M-C bonds in $\text{Ph}_5\text{As/Sb}$ with electrophiles are rare¹. These cleavage reactions provide a suitable route for synthesising various organometallic derivatives⁴ and to introduce functional group into aromatic ring at predetermined positions⁵. Such cleavages also afford an insight into the strength of metal-carbon bond and the relative rates of elimination of phenyl group from pentaphenyl-arsenic or -antimony compounds. The conditions for the cleavage reaction described in this paper are uniform and mild and thus are advantageous over redistribution reactions only on As^{III} and Sb^{III} derivatives which need varying specific conditions^{1,4}. Although the cleavage of carbon-bismuth bond in R_3Bi with the above mentioned electrophiles has been previously reported^{2,6}, there appears to be no report of similar cleavages of phenyl-arsenic and -antimony compounds.

In view of our interest in group IVB metal-alkyl or -aryl bond(s) cleavages in symmetrical^{7,8} and unsymmetrical⁹ tetraorganometallics with halogens, inter-halogens, inter-pseudohalogens, thiocyanogen *etc.*, it was thought worthwhile to report the interaction of phenyl-arsine or -stilbene with halogens and inter-halogens. The main objectives of the present work are to investigate the changes brought about by using electrophiles on the phenyl group directly attached to metal-atom, and to compare the relative rate of electrophilic reagents on As-C, Sb-C bonds.

Experimental

Preparation: Pentaphenyl-arsenic or -antimony compounds were prepared as reported in an earlier publication². Iodine monochloride (Fluka) was distilled before use. Iodine monobromide was prepared by dissolving iodine in an excess of bromine and purified¹⁰. Anhydrous acetonitrile

was the solvent used throughout, and moisture was excluded during the reactions and their work-ups. Few typical experiments are described below.

Reaction of pentaphenylarsenic with ICl (1 : 2 ratio): Iodine monochloride (3.4 g, 0.0209 mol) in acetonitrile (20 ml) was slowly added to a well stirred and chilled cold (0°) suspension of pentaphenylarsenic (4.6 g, 0.0099 mol) in the same solvent (200 ml). The initial blood-red colour of ICl solution disappeared immediately after each addition. The mixture was further stirred for 30 min to ensure complete reaction and then worked up. The solvent was distilled off to give a colourless liquid, b.p. 63-65°/10 mm (lit.¹¹ 184-80°); whose ir spectrum was identical with that of an authentic sample of PhI. The residue (after distilling off PhI) was recrystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and identified as triphenylarsenic dichloride (2.14 g, 70%), m.p. 205° (lit.¹² 205°).

Reaction of pentaphenylantimony with I_2 (1 : 1 ratio):

A solution of I_2 (2.72 g, 0.0107 mol) in methyl cyanide (20 ml) was added dropwise for 30 min to a well stirred solution of pentaphenylantimony (5.4 g, 0.0106 mol) in CH_3CN (200 ml) at room temperature. The violet colour of I_2 disappeared after each addition. Towards the end of the reaction the solution changed its colour to pink. Subsequently, the solution was stirred for 1 h. It was freed from solvent, and phenyl iodide distilled off at 63-65°/10 mm (lit.¹¹ 184-80°); whose ir spectrum was superimposable with that of an authentic sample. The residue was recrystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) to give Ph_4SbI (84%), m.p. 200° (lit.¹³ 200°).

Measurements: Carbon, nitrogen and metal analyses were obtained from C.D.R.I., Lucknow, and halogens estimated gravimetrically as silver halides in the laboratory. The molar conductance of 10^{-3} M solutions of the compounds in anhydrous benzene were measured by a direct reading con-

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ductivity bridge using an immersion type conductivity cells. Infrared spectra ($4000-250\text{ cm}^{-1}$) of all the compounds were recorded in KBr on a Perkin-Elmer Infra-ray Cord and Carl Zeiss (U.R.-10) prism spectrophotometers. Melting points were determined with a Gallenkamp melting point apparatus in glass melting point tubes with one open end. The molecular weights of the compounds determined by the Rast Camphor method correspond to the formula weight, indicating their monomeric nature.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Mol. weight Found/ (Calcd.)
	O	X ^a	M ^b	
Ph ₅ AsBr ₂	46.90 (46.39)	33.36 (34.29)	16.21 (16.07)	466.90 (466.04)
Ph ₄ AsBr ₃	33.92 (34.54)	50.98 (51.07)	11.02 (11.97)	625.26 (625.85)
Ph ₄ AsI	55.68 (56.49)	24.60 (24.87)	14.24 (14.68)	503.90 (510.25)
Ph ₃ AsI ₂	38.20 (38.60)	44.90 (45.31)	13.01 (13.37)	560.28 (567.05)
Ph ₃ AsI ₃	25.98 (26.56)	61.50 (62.37)	8.98 (9.20)	813.30 (813.85)
Ph ₃ AsCl ₂	57.02 (57.32)	17.90 (18.8)	19.56 (19.86)	376.56 (377.14)
Ph ₄ AsBr	61.69 (62.22)	16.68 (17.24)	15.92 (16.17)	463.06 (463.25)
Ph ₄ SbBr ₂	41.26 (42.15)	30.56 (31.16)	23.34 (23.73)	512.56 (512.86)
Ph ₄ SbI	52.58 (51.74)	22.06 (22.78)	21.48 (21.85)	556.31 (557.08)
Ph ₃ SbI ₂	35.02 (35.62)	42.01 (41.82)	19.86 (20.06)	606.26 (606.87)
Ph ₃ SbCl ₂	50.06 (50.99)	15.90 (16.72)	28.62 (28.71)	423.58 (423.98)
Ph ₄ SbBr	56.08 (56.51)	14.92 (15.66)	23.42 (23.86)	509.52 (510.08)

^a Corresponding halide (Cl, Br, I). ^b As/Sb.

Results and Discussion

In continuation of our work⁷⁻⁹ on electrophilic cleavage of symmetrical and unsymmetrical tetraorganometallics with various electrophiles, we observed that both mono- and di-cleavages occur. This prompted us to present our results on the preparation of triphenyl-metal(VB) dihalides, tetraphenyl-metal(VB) halides and some triphenylarsenic tetrahalides from electrophilic cleavage of arsenic- and antimony-phenyl bond with various electrophiles.

Reactions with halogens and inter-halogens : Reactions of pentaphenylarsenic with halogens and inter-halogens were carried out successively at a lower temperature (0°) to give triphenylarsenic dihalides alongwith the corresponding amount of phenyl halide in excellent yields.

Unexpectedly, cleavage of two phenyl groups was observed with both Br₂ and ICl irrespective of the ratio of electrophiles used^{8,14}. It is interesting to note that iodine monochloride generally undergoes similar reactions as bromine under the iden-

tical conditions, so that under any circumstances when bromine can be used to produce an organometallic bromides, the corresponding chlorides can be obtained with iodine monochloride,

Cleavage with one mole of bromine and iodine monochloride was not successful under similar condition presumably due to the strong electrophilic nature of bromine and iodine monochloride and unreacted Ph₅As (0.5 mol) was recovered in each case. Addition of an excess of bromine (> 3 mol) to the solution of pentaphenylarsenic yielded a red precipitate of triphenylarsenic tetrabromide :

Reactions with I₂ and IBr : However, I₂ and IBr being weaker electrophiles^{5,14}, the reactions with these electrophiles proceeded less readily. Thus, 1 : 1 molar reaction of I₂ and IBr with Ph₅As produced Ph₄AsI and Ph₄AsBr, respectively, at room temperature,

I₂ and IBr cleaved one more phenyl group from Ph₄AsX on refluxing in methyl cyanide. Pentaphenylarsenic compounds was found to react smoothly under similar condition with an excess of iodine (> 3 mole) in methyl cyanide to give triphenylarsenic tetraiodide.

Reaction with pentaphenylantimony : Bromination of pentaphenylantimony produced triphenylantimony dibromide at 0°, irrespective of the molar ratio of bromine used. However, iodine cleavage of Ph₅Sb yielded tetraphenylantimony iodide with 1 mole of I₂ and triphenylantimony diiodide with 2 moles of I₂, respectively. Addition of three moles of bromine and iodine was not successful in producing triphenylantimony tetrahalides presumably due to the reduced nucleophilic character of antimony-phenyl bonds in triphenylantimony dihalides as compared to that in pentaphenylantimony. Reactions of iodine monochloride with pentaphenylantimony invariably produced Ph₃SbCl₂ at a lower temperature, irrespective of the molar ratio of the electrophiles used. Thus, 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar reactions of IBr with Ph₅Sb gave Ph₄SbBr and Ph₃SbBr₂ at room temperature and 70°, respectively.

The extent of cleavage is confined only to the removal of two phenyl groups from pentaphenylarsenic or -antimony compounds with iodine monochloride and iodine monobromide which was confirmed by treating the pentaphenylarsenic or -antimony compounds with an excess amount (> 2 mole) of the iodine-halides. Formation of diphenyl-metal (VB) trihalides did not take place even on prolong stirring. This observation is also supported by the fact that iodine monochloride did

not decolourise in refluxing CH_3CN when treated against Ph_3MCl_2 , and unreacted starting material was recovered quantitatively. An argument in favour of cleavage of two phenyl groups from pentaphenylarsenic is also based on the observation that a similar reagent Br_2 reacts with Ph_3AsBr_2 to produce Ph_3AsBr_4 . No further cleavage was observed.

The observation made with IBr and I_2 are in line with the fact that the $\text{Sb}-\text{C}$ bond is more reactive than $\text{As}-\text{C}^{1,15}$. Also the fission of second $\text{As}-\text{C}$ in these reactions proceeds less readily due to reduced nucleophilic character of $\text{As}-\text{C}$ bond coupled with the less polar nature of IBr and I_2 . However, there seems to be no kinetic study so far which have been carried out on this second fission reactions in pentaphenyl arsenic. The mechanism of such reactions may possibly involve a four centered transition state in which nucleophilic attack on metal atom (facilitated by the availability of vacant d-orbitals) by incipient chloride or bromide ion is synchronous with electrophilic attack by incipient iodide ion on carbon atom of the aromatic rings. Similar mechanism^{6,7-9} has earlier been suggested for the cleavage of group IVB compounds with halogens and interhalogens.

From the results reported above and from our earlier investigations, the reactivity was found to be in the orders, $\text{Br}_2 \approx \text{ICl} > \text{IBr} > \text{I}_2$, and $\text{As}-\text{C} < \text{Sb}-\text{C} > \text{Bi}-\text{C}$, which is also the decreasing order of their bond polarity. This supports to mechanism proposed above where electrophiles with greater bond polarity are expected to be more reactive.

Infrared spectra: The infrared spectroscopic results provide support for the molecular constitution of these compounds. The spectra of all the compounds show identical bands due to the phenyl group. Most infrared spectra were similar in this region and the identifying features for a specific compound were limited; consequently, this region will not be considered further. The metal-halogen stretching frequency in the spectra of the synthesised compounds are not observed in the $4000-250 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region. This leaves little doubt about the assignment of the stretching mode of the metal-halogen bonds. Similarly, no definite assignment can be made for the metal-carbon stretching

vibrations due to the presence of the phenyl bands. The study¹⁶ of the vibrational spectra of these compounds of the main group V elements indicates that metal-carbon stretching vibrations occur below 300 cm^{-1} . However, due to overlap with the phenyl ring vibrations below 300 cm^{-1} the assignments can not be made unequivocally.

Based on the elemental analysis and various physicochemical studies, the above synthesised compounds are found to be ionic and monomeric in benzene. All the compounds have 5-coordinate structure with the exception Ph_3AsX_4 which have 7-coordinate structures in the solid state.

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